

HARNESSING TECHNOLOGY: GEOGEBRA AND ITS INFLUENCE ON HIGH SCHOOL MATHEMATICS LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract. *This paper investigates the influence of GeoGebra, a dynamic mathematics software, on high school math learning outcomes. GeoGebra is a powerful tool that integrates geometry, algebra, and calculus through interactive visualizations, thus potentially enhancing student engagement and conceptual understanding. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature and empirical studies, this research explores how GeoGebra facilitates active learning, promotes problem-solving skills, and supports deeper mathematical reasoning among high school students. Additionally, the article examines the challenges and benefits associated with integrating GeoGebra in traditional mathematics instruction. The findings underscore GeoGebra's positive impact on improving students' mathematical proficiency and fostering a more interactive and collaborative learning environment in school classrooms.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, problem-solving, GeoGebra, geometry, visualization, mathematics.*

INTRODUCTION.

The integration of technology into mathematics education is essential for preparing students for success in the digital age. Interactive tools and platforms can transform complex mathematical concepts into engaging and relatable experiences. By offering personalized learning paths and immediate feedback, technology empowers students to grasp mathematical ideas at their own pace. This approach not only enhances learning but also cultivates crucial skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy, which are indispensable for future endeavors.

The integration of technology into education has ushered in a new era of learning, transforming traditional classrooms into dynamic and interactive spaces. One such tool, GeoGebra, has emerged as a powerful ally in enhancing mathematics education at the all-school level. This article delves into the potential of GeoGebra in revolutionizing how students perceive, understand, and apply mathematical concepts. By examining the impact of this dynamic software on learning outcomes, we aim to shed light on its role in shaping future-ready mathematicians.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS:

The usage of technology in education increases quality and provides the opportunity of raising technology-based generations [1]. The important way to develop an effective and more captivating teaching-learning environment for students is enable to participate in the lessons by managing the lesson with different stimuli. Therefore, using computer in educational environment has become a factor that provides stimuli richness [2]. Thus, the term of computer-based education means that using GeoGebra to help teachers to enrich lessons and upgrade the quality during learning-teaching activities.

According to the researchers, technology-oriented mathematics education enhanced students' understanding of basic concepts [3]. Using GeoGebra in mathematics, which any student can download the software onto their electronic device at no cost, can emerge mathematical understanding, both procedural and conceptual, and experiment and visualize. The straightforward manner in which GeoGebra developers designed the software's user interface corresponds well with the principles of cognitive load during learning. Multimedia environments provide novel approaches to both learning and teaching when compared with traditional environments [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The main purpose of this study was to examine the effect of GeoGebra in the teaching and learning of mathematics in Fergana schools. The objective of this study was to determine the effectiveness of using GeoGebra on students' learning of graphs as compared to the traditional approach. The experimental research in which semi-structured interview forms which are managed by researchers, were used to take the opinions of students about the usage of GeoGebra software program in math education. Besides, after interview test was taken from students which are made to check students' knowledge. This pre-test-post-test is not equivalent control group design was used to examine the effectiveness of GeoGebra software in teaching and learning mathematics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Mathematics teachers have consistently faced scrutiny regarding their instructional methods and approaches aimed at maintaining student engagement, encouraging the application of problem-solving and critical thinking skills, and demonstrating the practical relevance of mathematics beyond high school. Using GeoGebra is essential way to improve such skills in order to use traditional style of lecturing (Figure 1). Students can understand abstract mathematical concepts by visualizing their graphs or shapes, as a result of this they can save these in their mind easily or they are engaged math classes. Because if students cannot imagine what their teachers say they will have no interests for lesson or they cannot remember this class.

Figure 1. Animation of increasing and decreasing of function.

All students create differently, so some students can enjoy learning mathematics while others cannot. According to researchers, working with GeoGebra can enhance to motivate students learning mathematics with its various interface, manipulating geometric shapes, algebraic equations, graphs and more easy-to-use facilities (Figure2).

Figure 2. Changes of function by using sliders

Many researchers have also reported GeoGebra software having positive effects on students' achievements and understanding mathematics. We had 75 high school students participate in the study. In total, 45 of the students were in the experimental group where students could use GeoGebra while 30 of the students were placed in the control group in which traditional learning methods were used. We checked both quantitative and qualitative approaches to collect information on student achievements. As a result of pre-test and post-test showed us using GeoGebra has more effective to visualize spatial shapes, changes of functions, and understand abstract mathematical concepts easily. However, students who were in the experimental group and the control group scored very similar to each other in the pre-test, while the average score was 17.92 and 17.02 respectively in the post-test. Thus, we concluded that students who learned through integrating learning methods with the support of GeoGebra increased student achievements. One of the tasks was to find the surface area formed by the intersection of the given two different functions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Surface formed by the intersection of the given functions

There have been researchers that also noted that the students who used GeoGebra gained more conceptual knowledge while the students who received the traditional style of teaching received more procedural knowledge. Although both conceptual and procedural knowledge is important for students to obtain better understanding in their academic achievements [5].

Therefore, according to the researchers, it can be showed that GeoGebra helped students in the achievements and understanding of mathematics.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the researchers' conclusion and my own research results, it is obvious that teaching and learning needs to change. In addition to learning the mathematics concepts, students and teachers also need to learn technological century skills. The new form of teaching and learning takes out of the traditional role and makes them more as a facilitator of knowledge. One of the most beneficial ways to switch the role of any teacher is to use technology in an appropriate way. As a result of using GeoGebra applets students develop a stronger sense of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Eventually, students showed an increase in their engagement and motivation while using GeoGebra. This research project illustrates other mathematics teachers should try to use this software in order to take them from the traditional role of teaching to one that is facilitator.

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